

Innovations in the Educational System

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Abstract: *In recent years, a lot of practical work has been carried out in our country, especially regarding the process of education and upbringing. In this article, the idea is that modern methods of education and training, innovative pedagogical technologies, and other educational systems are being implemented in all educational institutions, vocational schools, general secondary and secondary special educational institutions. - comments are made. A lot of conditions are being created by our state for our youth, regardless of their field.*

Key words: *Innovation, education, pedagogical process, modern, technological process, new ideas, socio-pedagogical, knowledge.*

In pedagogy, there are several concepts of the "education" category at the same time. Understanding education as a specially organized process of conveying the most important social experiences to the generation studying education is one of the most common concepts. Based on this, it is correct to conclude that teaching is the basis of any educational process. In this case, the educational process begins to be seen with didactic tools. The very concept of the educational system loses its autonomy and review specificity and becomes "drawn" into didactics. In order to "preserve" the educational process of its originality, "Education, education... education!" co-authors of the monograph V.A. Karakovskii, Novikova, Selivanova use another concept of it proposed by the famous Estonian pedagogue and psychologist O. YO. Laimete. If we look at the education process "according to Laymete", then the education system will not consist of didactics, but on the one hand, it will consist of a psychological-pedagogical system, and on the other - a social-pedagogical system.

In turn, the educational system affects students not only didactically (through teachers, lessons, textbooks, homework), but also as a social factor and through the involvement of students in the environment. ; it is influenced by the relations between parents, teachers and students, by a certain psychological environment created in each educational institution.

The concept of "didactic system" has been formed in pedagogy for a long time. The didactic system of the college is expressed through educational goals, content of study, methods and forms of its organization. Of course, educational goals are also implemented in the teaching process by determining the content of the studied material, the form and methods of its delivery. But in the logic of the second concept of education, the didactic system itself participates in the didactic system of the educational system, that is, it is its system. The educational task of the educational institution is, first of all, to form values for the world, culture, and environment in students, to realize themselves in this world, to find their place among others. But this task cannot be performed only in the process of education: it is also related to play, work, and creative activities within the framework of recreation related to the satisfaction of individual interests. Thus, in particular, there will be an opportunity to study the innovations of the education system. In the process of its creation and development, it is always necessary to solve a number of specific issues: the above-mentioned authors emphasize five of them:

- Forming a holistic and scientifically based view of the world in students.
- Formation of civic self-awareness, responsibility for the fate of the homeland.

- Attracting students to universal human values, forming among them the behavior corresponding to these values.
- Formation of prospective, "creativity" as personality traits in the growing future generation.
- Forming self-awareness, helping the student in self-realization.

Of course, the list of these issues can be continued. But in any case, these tasks themselves show the "uniqueness" of the educational tasks listed above.

As well as the in-depth discussion of the possibilities of the emergence and formation of innovations in various aspects of the above-mentioned didactic views, in this issue, we will study the educational innovations in the philosophical and technological aspects of the educational system.

The philosophical aspect of the consideration of the education system is to justify the content and goals of education, its concretization and the connection with the desired content of education. As we said earlier, under today's views, there are two different conceptual (in many ways opposite) approaches to the education system.

The first approach education is based on having a specific content (philosophical-pedagogical, ideological, psychological-pedagogical, spiritual and other), socially defined and purposeful impact on the personality of the student. . Such education is carried out in certain forms (frontal, group, individual) and with certain methods.

In this paradigm of "Education as influence", the pedagogue should achieve effective educational influence by all measures. He (the pedagogue) himself becomes the main subject in this system, without the equally valuable participation of children and parents, because children participate in the role of "leaders". And, of course, they are not considered equal partners in education. Here, the student participates as a "subject of education" and the reference to subjectivity as a student's activity always has the characteristic of what is called "active learning of the need" or adaptive activity.

This approach is directly related to the category of socialization that we introduced earlier, in which we consider the human acquisition of historically developed social rules, values, attitudes, ways of relating to spiritual and material culture. we understand the process. According to the generally accepted type, educating a student (in this explanation) means bringing him into the world of adults, teaching him to live "as one" according to common laws. Thus, socialization assumes that a person has the ability of "adaptive activity" and appropriate processes (teaching and upbringing) in preschool, school, special vocational colleges and random factors (family, mass media, number 'talking to the horse') is done under the influence.

The education system (or socialization) of this influence cannot be evaluated as contrary to humanity, because it does not necessarily have to be carried out by authoritative means. Humane relations between teachers and students can exist in it, humanitarian values can be promoted, elements of group and individual creativity can be implemented.

In addition, the educational system of influence should introduce democratic values and rules into the educational process itself (following changes in the environment): mastering democratic methods of organizing life (starting from the student community), in relation to others follow the mastery of rights and obligations.

However, this approach to education is related to the environment, because the character and life of the child in this case are completely determined by external forces. And then there is no chance to make a simple choice. Some kind of educational content that needs to be conveyed, social-pedagogical-theoretical coming from this educational standard, all this requires methods directed not at the internal "I

want" desire of the student, but at the external "need" requirement. Therefore, this educational system cannot exist without some kind of punishment and coercion.

A different approach to education is related to the creation of a humanitarian educational system. This approach is first of all compatible with the process of individualization that we discussed in detail in the previous section (but it should not be confused with the approach related to the goal of the child mastering the issues of socialization as well as possible). We remind you once again that individuation - in our understanding - is the responsibility of adults and the student himself to maintain and develop the unique, separate and unique that the student has or has acquired in his individual experience. activities.

Individualization, first of all, involves the provision of individually oriented support to the primary basic needs. Without it, it is impossible to feel the natural "self". Secondly, the physical, intellectual, and emotional abilities that have been brought up (inherited) specific to this individual provide for the creation of conditions for the maximum and free realization of opportunities. And finally, the third sign and main feature of individualization is to help a person in building an autonomous spiritual self, in creative embodiment of himself, in developing the ability to "non-adaptive activity", in choosing his own path in life.

The individualization of the person and the development of his "identity" thus constitutes a humanistic educational system in a broad sense. For this, in this educational system, special tools are developed that help people to realize themselves and realize themselves. Now, not only the pedagogue, but also the students themselves are the subjects of the humanistic educational system (this is its main difference from the influencing educational system, in which the child is considered the object of education). In this paradigm, both pedagogues and students jointly define the goals of vocational colleges, raise them to the level of practical tasks and implement them in cooperative activities. An important condition for the effectiveness of the humanistic educational system of the college is the unification of students and adults into a common team (although they differ in their tasks: students, pedagogues, parents). Interaction between students and adults creates certain relationships, which primarily determine the educational possibilities of the system.

Relationships are a special concern of pedagogues. Any humanitarian educational system is a specific system. The environment plays a major role in its formation, operation and development, not only as an external influencing factor, but also as a component of this system itself.

At the end of the comparison and analysis of the two types of educational systems, we will mention separately that the educational system of influence and the humanistic educational system differ in the content of their subject.

The first, first of all, studies the social view of the world. The second system learns the method of self-learning. The educational system of influencing certain social rules, values, and attitudes does not consider the issue of developing students' self-awareness - this is not considered its subject.

Humane educational system is another matter. As a person participates as a subject of selection, it is expected that he will make this choice in relation to himself, which means that this system cannot be implemented without the process of self-awareness. Therefore, various humanitarian educational systems are currently developing in this direction. Remembering the working (practical) concept of innovation (understood as the introduction of newness in general), we will show how innovation is formed when looking at the educational system from a philosophical point of view.

In each of the presented approaches, innovation is always associated with some new idea, even if it is considered a refinement of one of the approaches. For example, discussing the humanitarian paradigm of education, O.S. Gazman, first of all, connects the goal of education with the idea of self-development and pedagogical support. Many contemporary authors, studying the humanitarian paradigm, approach self-development (or the development of one's "identity") from different angles, following the

development of the individual. Some authors proceed from the broad meaning of this word: bringing oneself to the generality, characteristics for all people, being suitable for everyone, that is, they deviate from the context of one or another social ideological requirements, recognize the importance of universality in the development of oneself. they emphasize.

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